

UZBEKISTAN AND ITS ACHIEVEMENTS DURING THE PERIOD OF INDEPENDENCE

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Main stages: Development of the country

1. 1991 – 2016 The period of gaining Independence by Uzbekistan
2. 2017 – 2024 The period of development of the New Uzbekistan

Abstract: This article covers the achievements and successes of Uzbekistan during the years of independence. After independence, the country has achieved rapid development in the economy, politics, culture and social spheres. The article provides information about the reforms implemented by the Uzbek government, achieving economic stability, improving the living standards of the population, changes at the national and international levels, and achievements in foreign policy. In addition, the article examines Uzbekistan's international cooperation, attracting investments, progress in education and science, as well as its successes in preserving and developing cultural heritage. These achievements serve to strengthen the republic's position in the international arena.

Keywords: Independence, Republic, New Uzbekistan Development Strategy of the New Uzbekistan diplomacy politics economics, education sports culture partnership with other countries.

The history of the development of Uzbekistan after the collapse of the USSR is of particular importance. Since August 31, 1991, Uzbekistan became an independent Republic. From that moment on, the country had the opportunity to follow a modern new historical course. Developing the country and society in the country during the 33-year period of Independence, important political, economic and social reforms were carried out. Which affected public administration of the economy, politics, culture, sports, medicine and foreign diplomatic relations of the army and other areas.¹

All these changes would not have been possible without the activities and role of the First President of the Republic of Uzbekistan I. A. Karimov.

The main principles of the policy of the first president were:

<https://islomkarimov.uz/ru/>

<https://tass.ruhttps://tsargrad.tv/news/islam-karimov->

1. Development of the economy.
2. Increasing the role of democracy and social justice in the country.
3. Normalization of foreign diplomatic relations with neighboring countries.
4. Work was carried out in the social sphere.
5. And the state and political system was reformed.

In particular, it is worth noting the programs and strategies developed by the first president of the Republic of Uzbekistan. For the development and stabilization of the economy, the development of national values, culture and mentality. First of all, the first stage - from 1991 to 2000 - took a particularly significant, truly historical place in the life of our country and people - the stage of priority reforms and transformations of the transition period and the formation of the foundations² national statehood. In particular, changes have been achieved in the state and political system, a system of power has been developed, the country's symbols have been adopted, changes have been achieved in industry, oil, gas, gold, natural resources, all these factors have seriously influenced the development of the country, transport has also been greatly developed, the aviation industry, the railway industry, urban architecture has developed, cities such as Bukhara, Samarkand, Tashkent, Khiva, Fergana, Andijan have important historical and cultural significance in the history of our country, culture is the main element that allows us to expressively introduce the history and traditions of the country, during the period of independence, major work was carried out to reconstruct historical and spiritual centers, madrassas, mosques, scientific academies, museums, monuments, I. Karimov has repeatedly emphasized the importance of "strengthening the influence and effectiveness of the work carried out today in the cultural and educational sphere and based on the life-tested principle of "High spirituality is an invincible force." This principle became the title of one of the fundamental works of the first president of the Republic of Uzbekistan, published in 2008, which contains the Concept of spiritual development of independent Uzbekistan. In Uzbekistan, there are more than 8 thousand objects of historical, cultural, architectural, archaeological value, of which 545 are architectural, 575 are historical, 1457 are monuments of art, more than 5500 archaeological objects. This system includes more than 300 museums and 1200 enterprises of folk art. A lot of work has been done in the republic to reconstruct Islamic architectural monuments. Thus, the Imam Bukhari complex was built in Bukhara. In 2007, on the initiative of the head of state, the architectural complex of

² <https://vuzlit.com/https://files.student-it.ru/previewfile/191716>

Hazrati Imam, famous throughout the Islamic world, was reconstructed. Moreover, after gaining independence, Uzbekistan has done a lot of work to develop diplomatic and foreign policy relations, building a competent strategy for cooperation with other countries. Among which Russia, China, the USA, India, the countries of Central Asia and the countries of Western Europe stand out in particular. Cooperation is carried out in various areas and in various spheres: culture, sports, education, science, the army, medicine - these areas are priority areas. At the moment, regional and international organizations of the UN, the EU, NATO, the CIS, the CSTO, the SCO, and other organizations play an important role in the international agenda and strategy of Uzbekistan.

Uzbekistan closely cooperates with the UN and its specialized agencies in countering drug aggression. Successfully carried out interaction in this area with the UN Office on Drugs and Crime through the implementation of specific practical projects aimed at developing the potential of the relevant ministries and departments. At the suggestion of the Uzbek side, the Central Asian Regional Information Coordination Center for Combating Illicit Trafficking in Narcotic Drugs, Psychotropic Substances and Their Precursors (CARICC) was established.

Uzbekistan makes an effective contribution to the reconstruction of Afghanistan. At the initiative of the Head of Uzbekistan, an International Transport and Logistics Hub was created in Termez to ensure centralized and targeted delivery of humanitarian supplies to Afghanistan. The capabilities of Termez are actively used by the Office of the United Nations High Commissioner for Refugees, the World Food Program, UNICEF and other UN agencies.

Since 2017, Uzbekistan began to open a new page in its history with the coming to power of Sh. M. Mirziyev. New prospects and opportunities have appeared in the development of the country. The basis for this was the development strategy for the future of the New Uzbekistan.³ The period of change of the country is an important step on the path of development and progress. Such concepts as friendship, good neighborliness, strategic partnership, global regional and international problems became the basis of the country's development. Development of the system of cooperation in the sphere of industry, energy, transport, Tourism, education, science, and technology. With the attraction of attention of international investments, building a humane state by raising the honor and dignity of a person and further development of a free civil society;

³ <https://lex.uz/docs/5841077>

transformation of the principles of justice and the rule of law into a fundamental and necessary condition for the development of the country;

accelerated development of the national economy and ensuring high growth rates;

implementation of a fair social policy, development of human capital;

ensuring spiritual development and raising this sphere to a new level;

approach to global problems based on national interests;

strengthening the security and defense potential of the country, pursuing an open, pragmatic and active foreign policy. Openness development of the country achievements in sports in the education system with the rules of international standards development of all necessary areas of the country and strengthening its authority in the international arena priority tasks for Uzbekistan today 33 years of history of Independent Uzbekistan showed what achievements the country has made during this period in different areas friendship with neighboring countries open cooperation in the field of trade industry economy transport education culture achievements in sports and other industries will allow us to say with confidence that the country is developing rapidly President Sh. M. Mirziyoyev, having developed and approved the development strategy, outlined specific goals directions and priorities for the development of the New Uzbekistan Take into account that the Strategy "Uzbekistan - 2030" reflects the following main ideas:

joining the number of states with an above-average income through sustainable economic development;

creation of an education, medicine and social protection system that fully meets the needs of the people and international standards;

creation of favorable environmental conditions for the population;

building a fair and modern state serving the people;

guaranteed provision of sovereignty and security of the country.

Having prioritized these goals that directly affect the social sphere, the President made it clear that the State will fully pay attention to social and political issues, attracting the attention of International organizations, funds and countries China Russia Turkey Western European countries USA The Central Asian countries are the main partners in cooperation. It is especially worth noting that Uzbekistan has a constructive dialogue with neighboring States in the region within the framework of the organization. Consultative meetings of the Central Asian countries, where the leaders of the countries discuss issues of regional development and cooperation between the countries. On the main directions and issues and aspects of cooperation. Uzbekistan has managed to seriously and qualitatively change the strategy of its foreign policy. The main task of which is security, stability, preservation of

sovereignty, tolerance, friendship, peacefulness and justice. 33 years of history of independent Uzbekistan have shown that the country has achieved great success.

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